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Research Article

**BARRIERS AND FACILITATORS TO ORGANIZE EVIDENCE
BASED MANAGEMENT IN NURSING**¹Qammer Javed, ²Ms. Sana Sehar, ³Muhammad Afzal, ⁴Dr. Syed Amir Gilani.¹Student. The University of Lahore, ²Assistant professor. . The University of Lahore, ³associate professor. The University of Lahore, ⁴Dean faculty of allied health sciences. The University of Lahore.**Article Received:** October 2019 **Accepted:** November 2019 **Published:** December 2019**Abstract:**

Background Evidence based management is typically undertaken to improve practice. Although there have been many studies motivated on the obstacles and originators to implementing Confirmation centered organization.

Aims The purpose of the present study is to observe the fences and initiators to evidence-based practice (EBP) using Shortell's framework for continuous quality improvement.

Results Across the articles, the most common barriers were lack of time and lack of autonomy to change practice which falls within the deliberate and traditional magnitudes in Shortell's framework.

Conclusions Barriers and facilitators to EBP adoption occur at the individual and institutional levels. Solutions to the barriers need to be directed to the element where the barrier occurs, while recognizing that multidimensional styles are crucial to the achievement of overcoming these barriers.

Implications for nursing management the findings of the present study can help nurses identify barriers and implement strategies to promote evidence based management

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INTRODUCTION:

Evidence- based management (EBMgt) has been expanded as a new management model for improving the quality of healthcare organizations' decisions (Janati & Hasanpoor, 2017). Evidence-based management is about making decisions through the conscientious, explicit and judicious use of the best available evidence from multiple sources by Asking: Translating a practical issue or problem into an answerable question. Acquiring: Systematically searching and retrieving the evidence. Center for Evidence Based Management originally coined in the 1990s in the field of medicine, but today its principles extend in nursing.

Scenario:

Some health services institutions not providing high quality of care of patient due to lack of Evidence based practice. Student nurses are unaware about Evidence based practice during their starting clinical period. It is seen in public health at work place in an emergency department, there was patient came with the case of Traffic Road Accident. He was very sick and immune compromised. A nurse was changing the dressing of patient without wearing gloves. And then she was attending other patients with dirty hands. On duty doctors complaint the on duty nursing manager that x staff was attending the patient without wearing gloves. Nursing manager observed the entire situation and also observed the nurse's wrong practices at workplace and then she makes some polices regarding hand hygiene. She gives this polices to all the nursing departments and emphasized to follow all the instructions.

MANAGEMENT PROCESS:**(Problem Solving and Decision Making)**

In this scenario I identify that there was wrong practices were followed by the nurses and also patient care was compromised. I also observed and checked their methods and patient care practices which were very poor. They were handling the patients without gloves which are the ways to transfer infection to the patient due to negligence. Then, I applied the problem solving and decision making process management to overcome the situation and make the Polices of hand hygiene and also provide small workshops and synopsis about hand hygiene. I also check their knowledge regarding hand hygiene before and after workshops and sessions.

Decision making strategy is used to handle the problem occur in an organization.

1. Identify the problem
2. Analysis the problem
3. Develop alternative solutions
4. Select the best solution
5. Converting decision into action
6. Follow up of Action taken

The Problem-Solving & Management works involves the students complete self-inquiry, involvement of capabilities and best practices, and numerous opportunities to practice and apply the skills learned to relevant case studies—as well as to their own situations at work. Some of the elements we incorporate into the workshop include

- Case-studies
- Skill practice opportunities
- Tools and guides
- Experiential exercises

Problem Solving and Decision Making

- Problem
 - **A situation that exists when objectives are not being met.**
- Problem Solving
 - **The process of taking corrective action to meet objectives.**
- Decision Making
 - **The process of selecting an alternative course of action that will solve a problem.**
 - Managers need to make proficient decisions while performing the functions of management.

RESULTS:

After making the Polices about hand hygiene results were positive and followed by the nurses and doctors while attending the patients. Evidence based practices are the crucial part in improving the health status. Evidence based practice change the nursing practice in a clinical environment that support nursing autonomy and promote nursing care towards patient. It also helps managers to identify the problem and barriers which make the facilitators to provide the evidence based management. It makes the managers to make decisions. Decision making process is a dynamic process. The effective decisions are made in collaboration with other in the organization. Managerial factors include providing continuous education on EBP not only one time. On the other hand, they provide opportunity for staff to upgrade their skill for using in Evidence based management putting into practice and structural maintenance. Distinct factors contain inquiry culture and increasing nurses' awareness of strategies to implement Evidence based practice in the area of patient care. Study suggests that nurses need more continuous Evidence based practices educational programs as part of system to develop their knowledge and skills.

Theoretical framework of the study:

The theoretic structure was based on Melnyk and Fineout-Overholt's model (2005) of Progressing Investigation and Experimental Training complete Close Teamwork. This model hypothesizes a supportable means of implementing the processes of Evidence based practice. Made up of different steps, it allows organizations to generate conditions encouraging to the development of a culture of EBP, one which promotes positive beliefs and therefore its application. These steps involve the identification of helpers and obstacles to application and the development of a mentoring programmer within the organization to ensure the effectiveness and sustainability of the process. We assumed that more positive views about the value of EBP would be associated with better implementation (Melnyk&Fineout-Overholt's, 2005).

DISCUSSION:

Nursing managers are a very significant assembly in healthcare administrations and play important parts in hospital management, such as overwhelming fences to Evidence based management and assisting the application progress of Evidence based management.

The purpose of this research was to explore facilitators and barriers to implementation of Evidence based on nursing supervisors' viewpoints.

This study explored the factors that were barriers to Evidence based practices. The field of "teaching and examination systems" had highest mean scores. "The lack of knowledge about nursing producers and patient care. Knowledge producers are performers who plainly produce research- based, practice- based, or experience- based knowledge that can be shared with hospital decision- makers, such as nursing managers. They include groups such as academic researchers, program evaluators, and analysts who interpret research and data. As these barriers have high mean scores and intensive influence on the implementation of EBP, nursing managers must try to overcome barriers to Evidence based management. Moreover, they can use the organizers of EBP for overcoming weaknesses (Khodadadi, &Yousefi, 2017).

Nurses identified "the lack of communication between knowledge producers and hospital decision-makers" as a key fence in using and relating Evidence based management principles. It was rated as the top barrier in this study, which is consistent with other studies conducted in similar settings and organizational contexts (Liang & Rasa, 2011).

Study suggests that most participants have positive attitudes and that most believe that using evidence-based management can increase organization decision making. Evidence based hospital management can improve management decisions and facilitytransport, efficiency and efficiency. Since EBMgt is an emerging approach, its practice among hospital managers has been limited. Several factors exist at organizational and personal levels, which play different and considerable roles. We know that many healthcare managers lack EBMgt skills. Thus, they need to instigate evidence-based management through training organizations and research institutes. Our framework helps hospital managers to pursue the multiple evidence sources in knowledge utilization processes. Using six evidence sources, managers distinguish the best available evidence for management decisions and in an evidence-based decision-making process to make the best decision. To increase EBMgt benefits and use in hospitals, training organization and research institute staff must involve hospital managers to set research programs and to guide and facilitate evidence interpretation (Barends&Briner, 2014).

This study identified five concepts as facilitators and barriers in pain management for trauma patients: knowledge, attitude, professional communication, organizational aspects and patient input. We found

that the three concepts, knowledge, attitude and patient input, covered shared themes in the chain of care, despite the different positions, backgrounds and educational levels of respondents. s study identified five concepts as facilitators and barriers in pain management for trauma patients. Knowledge deficits, attitude problems and patient input were similar for the Emergency Medical Services and Departments setting, despite the different positions. The lack of specialized and organizational response ensued as new themes. Identified organizational features stressed the importance of the organizational implanting of the improvement of pain management. Change of clinical practice requires a complete approach at different levels. However, we think a shift in attitudes is needed, together with constant investigation and criticism to healthcare providers on loyalty to the evidence-based guidelines. Strategies to improve pain management need to be tailored to the chain of emergency care and the multi-professional group of emergency care providers (Berben et al, 2012).

CONCLUSION:

The outcomes of this education can monitor nursing managers to provide structures of evidence based management operation. Overcoming Evidence based management blocks is the first step in moving toward general application of Evidence based management in healthcare organizations. According to findings, by identifying facilitators and barriers to Evidence based management current education about Evidence based management for nursing managers is essential in order to enrich nurses' management knowledge and skills, and hospital management should take steps to diminish the barriers to Evidence based management operation. The lack of communication between knowledge producers and hospital decision- makers was one of main problems to using Evidence based management. Therefore, interaction between knowledge producers and nursing managers is an influential means by which to generate practice-relevant knowledge and permit evidence- informed practice. There is a need for implementing effective interventions in order to overcome the barriers to Evidence based management and to develop the facilitators at both organizational and individual levels to encourage nursing managers to change their practice to be based on evidences.

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